

A VARIANCE DECONVOLUTION APPROACH TO SAMPLING UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION FOR MONTE CARLO RADIATION TRANSPORT SOLVERS

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Abstract. Radiation transport computations in realistic systems are affected by the presence of uncertainty sources, *e.g.* nuclear cross section data and variability in geometric arrangement. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to statistically characterize the response of quantities of interest by performing efficient and accurate uncertainty quantification (UQ). Traditionally, UQ is focused on evaluating how the statistics, *e.g.* variance, of quantities of interest from a numerical code response are affected by sources of uncertainty, which can be propagated through several runs of the numerical code. For radiation transport problems, solved using Monte Carlo particle transport methods, one sample (in the parameter space) of the quantity of interest is obtained by averaging various particles' random walks, and, therefore, the non-deterministic nature of the solver itself introduces an additional source of variance. In this contribution, we describe how we can obtain efficient sample variance estimators by taking into account the additional variability introduced by a non-deterministic solver. We provide a rigorous mathematical treatment of these variance contributions and their sampling estimator counterparts. In particular, we present numerical test problems in which this variance deconvolution strategy is deployed with and without scattering, in 1D slabs, and with uncertain material properties. We also demonstrate how our novel estimator is more precise than a related variance estimator recently introduced in [9].

1. Introduction. Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) is the process of propagating sources of uncertainty through numerical codes in order to evaluate the statistics of Quantities of Interest (QoIs). It is nowadays well established that truly predictive numerical simulations can be obtained only when UQ is included in the analysis workflow. Over the years, several UQ strategies have been proposed to address different challenges; however, virtually all of them still face challenges when dealing with a large parameter dimension. Like other computational science applications, radiation transport applications are impacted by a large number of uncertainty sources, which roughly correspond to a number of uncertainty parameters that scale with the complexity of the models. In this contribution, we want to consider radiation transport applications in which a Monte Carlo transport method is used to evaluate the QoI and a sampling strategy, whose convergence is unaffected by the input parameter dimension, is then used for the UQ forward propagation. We note that two sources of uncertainty are often considered in UQ, namely epistemic and aleatory uncertainty. In this contribution we only consider aleatory uncertainties, which are sources of uncertainty that can be characterized and analyzed by using a statistical approach.

Monte Carlo (MC) methods can be used to solve for QoIs in a radiation transport problem as an alternate to deterministic methods, which explicitly solve the Boltzmann transport equation for a complete profile of average particle behavior throughout the phase space of the problem [2]. Instead, MC methods treat the physical system as a statistical process, using nuclear data to construct probability distributions that describe the various ways particles could behave in the system. Individual particles are simulated and their behavior (*e.g.* colliding with other particles, exiting the system, etc.) is recorded in tallies based on what information the user might want. The central limit theorem can then be applied to extrapolate the tallied behavior of the simulated particles to the average behavior of all particles in the system, with some associated uncertainty based on the number of particles simulated. Monte Carlo methods are useful depending on the information needed by the user or the problem space itself; for example, they can be used to handle complex

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geometries more effectively than deterministic solvers [2].

On the other end, UQ can be performed using a variety of strategies such as surrogates [7], sampling-based strategies [11], or hybrid strategies in which a sampling technique is used for the construction of a surrogate [1, 4, 8]. Sampling-based methods are generally more robust and flexible for applications characterized by noisy QoIs, poor solution regularity and large input dimensions, and, therefore, in this contribution we focus on them since these features are well suited for solving radiation transport problems based on MC transport solvers. Moreover, purely sampling approaches can be incorporated into hybrid approaches for the surrogate construction without extensive modifications, *e.g.* in the case of Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) (see [4, 8]). The main sampling method is Monte Carlo, which is a provably convergent method for obtaining statistics of problems with arbitrary dimension and regularity. Notably, MC is also popular due to the possibility of implementing it in an embarrassingly parallel fashion. Another important feature of MC is its ability to provide an estimate of the error in resolving statistics of the QoI, *e.g.* the expected value, and therefore provide a rigorous mathematical framework to assess its convergence. Our goal in this contribution is to show how these properties can be used to study the convergence properties of an MC UQ method applied to an MC radiation transport code. The combination of these strategies can be in fact interpreted as a nesting of two MC estimators for which convergence to the true statistics can be studied as a function of the number of both the UQ samples and radiation transport particles.

The remainder of this paper is organized as it follows. In Section 2, the theoretical contributions of the paper are introduced. In Section 3, the radiation transport problem that we want to solve is described along with the definition of the relevant uncertainty parameters. In Section 4, we present numerical results for several UQ scenarios concerning the 1D radiation transport problem in which we corroborate our theoretical findings. Concluding remarks close the paper in Section 5.

2. Theory for nested sampling estimators. In this section, we describe the mathematical foundations behind the use of sampling estimators for MC radiation transport (RT) codes. We present the nested estimators in a general context and highlight how these concepts can be applied to other applications in which there is a source of randomness that cannot be explicitly controlled, *i.e.* in the presence of a generic non-deterministic code. The framework that we want to present and analyze here consists of an MC sampling estimator for the UQ that is used to compute statistics (we will focus here on the variance) of a QoI.

We introduce here some definitions and the notation that will be used in the rest of the manuscript. We consider for simplicity a generic scalar QoI Q , which is a function of a vector of input parameters $\xi \in \Xi \subseteq \mathcal{R}^d$, where $d \in \mathcal{N}_0$ is the number of uncertain parameters. As is typical for UQ, we consider a joint probability density function $p(\xi)$ for ξ , such that $\int_{\Xi} p(\xi) d\xi = 1$.

Moreover, we are interested in computing (central) moments of Q , such as

$$\mathbb{E}[Q] = \int_{\Xi} Q(\xi) p(\xi) d\xi \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Var}[Q] = \int_{\Xi} (Q(\xi) - \mathbb{E}[Q])^2 p(\xi) d\xi, \quad (2.1)$$

with $\mathbb{E}[Q]$ and $\text{Var}[Q]$ denoting the mean and the variance of Q , respectively.

The MC approximations for the mean and variance can be written by drawing N_{ξ} samples for the QoI, each of them corresponding to the solution of a possibly expensive

computational code (the RT in our case), as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[Q] &\approx \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} Q(\xi^{(i)}) \\ \text{Var}[Q] &\approx \frac{1}{N_\xi - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \left(Q(\xi^{(i)}) - \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{k=1}^{N_\xi} Q(\xi^{(k)}) \right)^2.\end{aligned}\quad (2.2)$$

Both estimators in Eq. (2.2) are unbiased; for more details, the interested reader can refer, for instance, to [11].

In RT applications, as well in all applications involving non-deterministic codes [5], it is common to be interested in QoIs that are obtained as statistics of elementary and observable events. Without a loss of generality, we consider here observing an elementary realization $f(\xi, \eta)$ of each code run. We have introduced a random variable η , possibly a random vector, to notionally represent the code's stochastic behavior. We note here that the knowledge of η is neither implied nor required for the following derivation, however it reflects the fact that multiple realizations of the code will produce event realizations f corresponding to a different realization of η (even for a fixed UQ random input ξ). On the other hand, we assume to be able to sample ξ from $p(\xi)$ and to be able to obtain multiple code evaluations for the same value of ξ . In the RT case, the elementary event f would correspond to a particle history response (*i.e.* tally), ξ would be the set of UQ parameters, and η would be the inaccessible vector of random variables used by the code to generate the particle history and transport events (absorption, scattering, *etc.*) during a particle 'random walk.'

In the following, we consider that $Q(\xi)$ is obtained as an expected value of elementary events f over multiple realizations of η , generated internally in a non-deterministic code, as

$$Q(\xi) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{E}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)], \quad (2.3)$$

where $\mathbb{E}_\eta [\cdot]$ is a shorthand used to indicate the expected value over realizations drawn with respect to the variable η . For RT applications, this corresponds to the expected value over a number of particle histories. In practice, RT codes can only be queried a finite number of times for a fixed UQ parameter configuration, so the value of $\mathbb{E}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)]$ can only be approximated. Our contribution here is to understand the effect of the MC RT approximation of this term and how it propagates and affect the statistics we want to evaluate for the UQ. An MC estimator can be written for the approximation of Eq. (2.3) as

$$Q(\xi) = \mathbb{E}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)] \approx \frac{1}{N_\eta} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\eta} f(\xi, \eta^{(j)}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \tilde{Q}(\xi), \quad (2.4)$$

where our approximation $\tilde{Q}(\xi)$ also introduces the notation $\tilde{\cdot}$ to indicate a quantity that embeds the noise/stochasticity introduced by the MC solver, observed with a finite number of instances. If we combine Eqs. (2.2) and (2.4), we can obtain an MC-MC estimator for the expected value of the QoI

$$\mathbb{E}[Q] \approx \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} Q(\xi^{(i)}) \approx \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \tilde{Q}(\xi^{(i)}) = \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \left(\frac{1}{N_\eta} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\eta} f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(j)}) \right) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \hat{Q}, \quad (2.5)$$

where we introduced the notation $\hat{\cdot}$ to indicate a sample estimator over the UQ parameter space.

Our goal in the next sections is to present several features of this estimator and the variance estimator, under the assumption that the number of histories N_η is constant for each UQ sample. Though not strictly required, this simplifies the derivation while still providing insights into the more general case.

2.1. Statistical properties of the MC-MC estimator. In this section, we discuss the features of the MC-MC estimator. We start by considering the estimator bias

$$\mathbb{E} [\hat{Q}] = \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \tilde{Q}(\xi^{(i)}) \right] = \mathbb{E} [\tilde{Q}(\xi)] = \mathbb{E}_\xi [\mathbb{E}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)]] = \mathbb{E}_\xi [Q(\xi)], \quad (2.6)$$

where we explicitly indicate the space over which we compute the expected value¹.

The estimator is unbiased due to the linearity of the expected value operators, so it is important to study its variance to understand the impact of the number of both UQ samples N_ξ and histories N_η . The variance of the MC-MC estimator Eq. (2.5) is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var} [\hat{Q}] &= \text{Var} \left[\frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \left(\frac{1}{N_\eta} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\eta} f(\xi, \eta^{(j)}) \right) \right] \\ &= \text{Var} \left[\frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \tilde{Q}(\xi^{(i)}) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{N_\xi} \text{Var} [\tilde{Q}]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

The variance of the quantity \tilde{Q} is indeed a function of the set of samples drawn for both ξ and η . In order to evaluate this term, we can turn to the law of total variance

$$\text{Var} [Z(X, Y)] = \text{Var}_Y [\mathbb{E}_X [Z]] + \mathbb{E}_Y [\text{Var}_X [Z]], \quad (2.8)$$

where X, Y and $Z = Z(X, Y)$ are three random variables.

Applied to $\text{Var} [\tilde{Q}]$, the law of total variance provides a strategy to decompose this variance into the variance associated with the UQ parameters ξ and the variance associated with the set of particle histories η . It is important to remark here that, due to computational cost limitations, it is not always possible to obtain an approximation of \tilde{Q} with a large number of histories, in the context of a UQ workflow in which multiple \tilde{Q} should be evaluated for several values of the input vector ξ . Therefore, it is important to be able to quantify the additional estimator variance introduced by the MC over η , which can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var} [\tilde{Q}] &= \text{Var}_\xi [\mathbb{E}_\eta [\tilde{Q}]] + \mathbb{E}_\xi [\text{Var}_\eta [\tilde{Q}]] \\ &= \text{Var}_\xi \left[\mathbb{E}_\eta \left[\frac{1}{N_\eta} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\eta} f(\xi, \eta^{(j)}) \right] \right] + \mathbb{E}_\xi \left[\text{Var}_\eta \left[\frac{1}{N_\eta} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\eta} f(\xi, \eta^{(j)}) \right] \right] \\ &= \text{Var}_\xi [\mathbb{E}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)]] + \mathbb{E}_\xi \left[\frac{\text{Var}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)]}{N_\eta} \right] \\ &= \text{Var}_\xi [Q] + \mathbb{E}_\xi \left[\frac{\sigma_\eta^2}{N_\eta} \right] = \text{Var}_\xi [Q] + \mathbb{E}_\xi [\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2], \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

¹Please note that we do not always write explicitly that space and use $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ in order to simplify the notation whenever the integration variables are easy to identify by the context.

where σ_η^2 is defined as the variance of the histories for one fixed UQ parameter, *i.e.* $\sigma_\eta^2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Var}_\eta [f(\xi, \eta)]$, and $\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\sigma_\eta^2}{N_\eta}$ is the corresponding MC RT estimator variance. The expression above relates the true variance of the QoI with respect to the UQ parameters, $\text{Var}_\xi [Q]$, and the variability introduced by the use of a finite number of particle histories in the RT Monte Carlo solver, σ_{RT, N_η}^2 , averaged over the UQ parameter space. Both terms contribute to the polluted variance $\text{Var} [\tilde{Q}]$, which is the variance that one could observe by sampling the QoI obtained for each RT calculation using N_η particles. In practice, without realizing that an additional contribution to the variance is introduced by σ_{RT, N_η}^2 , a practitioner would overestimate the parameter variance by assuming $\text{Var}_\xi [Q] \approx \text{Var}_\xi [\tilde{Q}]$. Similarly, the variance of the MC-MC estimator for the QoI is obtained by combining Eqs. (2.7) and (2.9)

$$\text{Var} [\hat{Q}] = \frac{\text{Var}_\xi [Q] + \mathbb{E}_\xi [\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2]}{N_\xi}. \quad (2.10)$$

The goal of a precise estimator is to obtain statistics with the lowest possible variance for a prescribed computational budget. In the case of this MC-MC estimator with the assumption of constant N_η for all N_ξ UQ runs, the total computational budget is $\mathcal{C} = N_\xi \times N_\eta$. Therefore, it is possible to note how the variance $\text{Var} [\hat{Q}]$ is minimized for $N_\eta = 1$, which suggests that the most effective estimator for the mean is obtained by using a single particle history per UQ simulation². The interested reader can refer to [4], where these estimators have been discussed in the context of non-intrusive spectral projection for polynomial chaos computations. In the next section, we discuss the impact of the number of particles N_η in the variance estimation.

2.2. Variance deconvolution and practical implementation. The law of total variance allows for the decomposition of the total variance, namely $\text{Var}_\xi [\tilde{Q}]$, into two contributions: the true QoI variance, $\text{Var}_\xi [Q]$, and the average over the UQ parameter space of the noise introduced by the limited number of particle histories, $\mathbb{E}_\xi [\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2]$, which also corresponds to the estimator variance of the RT MC solver. A few considerations are in order here. In general, we are interested in characterizing the variance of the QoI $\text{Var}_\xi [Q]$, referred to hereafter simply as $\text{Var} [Q]$. However, we cannot access this quantity directly. As previously discussed, the QoI Q can be only approximated with \tilde{Q} , and this latter quantity can be considered to be polluted by MC noise. On the other hand, the possibility of obtaining several evaluations of \tilde{Q} (for several sample of ξ) makes its variance an accessible quantity, *i.e.* it can be estimated. Similarly, given multiple particle histories per UQ sample, it is possible to estimate the term $\sigma_\eta^2 = \text{Var}_\eta [f]$ at each UQ parameter location, and, consequently, σ_{RT, N_η}^2 .

It follows that the true variance can be written by removing the noise introduced by the finite number of particles from the polluted variance

$$\text{Var}_\xi [Q] = \text{Var} [Q] = \text{Var} [\tilde{Q}] - \mathbb{E}_\xi [\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2], \quad (2.11)$$

and its sample estimator counterpart can then be written as

$$\text{Var} [Q] \approx S^2 = \tilde{S}^2 - \hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2}, \quad (2.12)$$

²We note that in the case of $N_\eta = 1$, it would not be possible to estimate the term $\mathbb{E}_\xi [\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2]$.

where S^2 and \tilde{S}^2 represent the sample estimators for the true (inaccessible) and polluted variances, respectively and $\hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2}$ indicates the sample mean of the MC RT transport variance over the UQ space.

If the event associated with each particle history is available, *i.e.* $\{f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(j)})\}$ with $i = 1, \dots, N_\xi$ and $j = 1, \dots, N_\eta$, we can define

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{S}^2 &= \frac{1}{N_\xi - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \left(\tilde{Q}(\xi^{(i)}) - \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{k=1}^{N_\xi} \tilde{Q}(\xi^{(k)}) \right)^2 \\ \hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2} &= \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \frac{\sigma_\eta^2(\xi^{(i)})}{N_\eta},\end{aligned}\tag{2.13}$$

where the term σ_η^2 is approximated, for each UQ sample, with an additional sample variance estimator

$$\sigma_\eta^2(\xi^{(i)}) \approx \hat{\sigma}_\eta^2(\xi^{(i)}) = \frac{1}{N_\eta - 1} \sum_{j=1}^{N_\eta} \left(f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(j)}) - \frac{1}{N_\eta} \sum_{k=1}^{N_\eta} f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(k)}) \right)^2.\tag{2.14}$$

We note here that a similar variance deconvolution strategy has been also adopted for radiation problems in [9], in which an embedded implementation has been also discussed under the name of Embedded VAriance DEconvolution (EVADE). More recently, the EVADE algorithm has been also used to improve the efficiency of RT computations in the presence of stochastic media in [13]. The primary difference between Eq. (2.12) and the estimator adopted in [9] is that in [9], the total variance is written for the case of a single particle history per UQ sample, and therefore the term $\text{Var}[\tilde{Q}]$ is always approximated by using only one particle history. We discuss the properties of both estimators in more detail in the following section.

2.3. Connection with estimator proposed in [9]. We consider here the relationship between the estimator proposed in [9] and the estimator derived in Eq. (2.12). We first note that in the original estimator formulation, only one history per UQ sample was used in the computation of the variance $\text{Var}[\tilde{Q}]$, effectively approximating $\tilde{Q}(\xi^{(i)}) = f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(1)})$, even in the case where multiple particle histories were used for other calculations³.

If one particle history per sample is used we can write Eq. (2.12) as

$$\text{Var}[Q] \approx S_I^2 = \tilde{S}_I^2 - \hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2},\tag{2.15}$$

where

$$\tilde{S}_I^2 = \frac{1}{N_\xi - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\xi} \left(f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(1)}) - \frac{1}{N_\xi} \sum_{k=1}^{N_\xi} f(\xi^{(k)}, \eta^{(1)}) \right)^2.\tag{2.16}$$

As a first result, we note that the estimators \tilde{S}^2 , \tilde{S}_I^2 and $\hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2}$ are unbiased estimators,

³We note here that the notation $f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(1)})$ represents an useful conceptual aid, however the analysis would be exactly the same if $\tilde{Q}(\xi^{(i)})$ was approximated with a single particle history randomly picked among the vector $\{f(\xi^{(i)}, \eta^{(j)})\}_{j=1}^{N_\eta}$

i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[\tilde{S}^2 \right] &= \mathbb{E} \left[\tilde{S}_I^2 \right] = \text{Var}_\xi \left[\tilde{Q} \right] \\ \mathbb{E} \left[\hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2} \right] &= \mathbb{E}_\xi \left[\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2 \right], \end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

and, therefore, both estimators, S^2 and S_I^2 , are also unbiased estimators of $\text{Var} [Q]$.

On the other hand, the variances of the estimators S^2 and S_I^2 can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var} [S^2] &= \text{Var} \left[\tilde{S}^2 \right] + \text{Var} \left[\hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2} \right] - 2\text{Cov} \left[\tilde{S}^2, \hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2} \right] \\ \text{Var} [S_I^2] &= \text{Var} \left[\tilde{S}_I^2 \right] + \text{Var} \left[\hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2} \right] - 2\text{Cov} \left[\tilde{S}_I^2, \hat{\mu}_{\sigma_{RT,N_\eta}^2} \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

Although we are not providing here a closed-form solution for these terms, it is possible to infer that the variances associated to the terms involving \tilde{S}_I^2 would be larger than their counterpart for \tilde{S}^2 due to the larger number of histories used in the current estimator.

In the remainder of this paper, we provide numerical evidence on how the current estimator can be used for an efficient unbiased estimation of the parametric variance of a RT QoI and how the present formulation can outperform the estimator based on a coarse approximation of $\text{Var} \left[\tilde{Q} \right]$ for several UQ scenarios in radiation transport.

3. 1D Radiation Transport Problem. Both the MC-MC estimator developed in Section 2 and the estimator developed in [9] are applied here to an example radiation transport problem such that the inner MC loop is a Monte Carlo radiation transport solver described in further detail in Section 3.2, and the outer MC loop is over the UQ parameter space. Our goal is to provide an estimate of the variance of the QoI, over the UQ parameter space, which for this example problem is transmittance through a slab.

3.1. Problem Description. We solve the stochastic, one-dimensional, neutral-particle, mono-energetic, steady-state radiation transport equation with a normally incident beam source of magnitude one:

$$\mu \frac{\partial \psi(x, \mu, \xi)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_t(x, \xi) \psi(x, \mu, \xi) = \int_{-1}^1 d\mu' \psi(x, \mu', \xi) \frac{\Sigma_s(x, \mu' \rightarrow \mu, \xi)}{2}, \tag{3.1}$$

$$0 \leq x \leq L; \quad -1 \leq \mu \leq 1, \tag{3.2}$$

$$\psi(0, \mu, \xi) = 1, \mu > 0; \quad \psi(L, \mu, \xi) = 0, \mu < 0 \tag{3.3}$$

where $\psi(x, \mu, \xi)$ is angular flux, $\Sigma_t(x, \xi)$ is total cross section, $\Sigma_s(x, \mu, \xi)$ is scattering cross section, and $x, \mu,$ and ξ respectively denote dependence on space, angle, and the vector of independent uncertain variables. The problem boundaries are fixed, *i.e.* $x \in [0, L]$, as are the locations between material regions. The problem is solved for two different scenarios: attenuation only, in which $\Sigma_s(x, \mu, \xi) = 0$; and with both attenuation and isotropic scattering. For both scenarios, the total cross section of each material is assumed to be uniformly distributed. In the scenario which also involves scattering, the ratio of scattering to total cross section c is distributed uniformly and independently of Σ_t . We consider a slab with a total of M materials, where for each region m the total cross section is defined as

$$\Sigma_{t,m}(\xi_m) = \bar{\Sigma}_{t,m} + \Sigma_{t,m}^\Delta \xi_m \tag{3.4}$$

with $\bar{\Sigma}_{t,m}$ representing the average total cross section and $\Sigma_{t,m}^\Delta$ the deviation from the mean value. Furthermore, a random parameter $\xi_m \sim \mathcal{U}[-1, 1]$ is used to represent the variability

of $\Sigma_{t,m}(\xi) \sim \mathcal{U}[\bar{\Sigma}_{t,m} - \Sigma_{t,m}^\Delta, \bar{\Sigma}_{t,m} + \Sigma_{t,m}^\Delta]$. For cases with scattering, the scattering ratio is defined analogously using

$$c_m(\xi_{M+m}) = \bar{c}_m + c_m^\Delta \xi_{M+m} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\xi_{M+m} \sim \mathcal{U}[-1, 1]$, with $m = 1, \dots, M$, is a uniformly distributed random variable. We note that in the attenuation-only case the problem contains a number of uncertain parameters equal to the number of materials, *i.e.* $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d = M$, whereas in the case of both attenuation and scattering $d = 2M$.

3.2. Monte Carlo Particle Transport and Woodcock Delta Tracking. Though Equation 3.1 can be thought of as the governing equation for this example problem, Section 1 points out that an estimate of our quantity of interest is obtained not by analytically or numerically solving the Boltzmann equation, but by averaging the tallied responses of individual particles [2]. In this example problem, the tallied QoI is transmittance; a response is tallied when a particle exits the far end of the slab, and a history is terminated when a particle is either absorbed or scatters to exit back through the beam-incident side of the slab. The series of random samples used to determine when the particle will reach a position of interest and what will happen when it does is described stochastically using η , as outlined in Section 2.

Particles’ ‘random walks’ begin with the initial conditions in Eq. (3.1). They’re moved through the system by randomly sampling the distance to their next collision⁴, d_c ,

$$d_c = \frac{-\ln(\Gamma)}{\Sigma_t}, \quad \Gamma \in [0, 1) \quad (3.6)$$

where Γ is a randomly sampled number on $[0, 1)$ [2]. Equation 3.6, and therefore the calculated distance to collision, remains accurate as long as Σ_t is constant. For homogeneous media where $\Sigma_{t,m}$ is constant across material m , this is uncomplicated⁵. However, for heterogeneous media modeled as having different material sections separated by boundaries, this can become computationally expensive [12]. If the distance to a boundary is less than the calculated distance to collision and the particle would move from material m to material m' , traditional collision-distance tracking methods only move the particle so far as the boundary location, then re-calculate d_c using $\Sigma_{t,m'}$ [12].

Instead, Woodcock-delta tracking calculates d_c using a majorant cross section Σ_M , which is typically taken to be the largest total cross section the particle might encounter along its direction of travel. Using the largest possible cross-section renders checking whether a particle has crossed a material boundary unnecessary; the probability of collision is either correct or overestimated, making the calculated distance to collision either correct or underestimated. This is corrected for by taking the ratio between Σ_t at the collision site and Σ_M to be the probability of whether the collision has actually occurred. For a particle moved to a possible collision site in material i , if for a randomly sampled $\omega \in [0, 1)$,

$$\omega < \frac{\Sigma_{t,i}}{\Sigma_M}, \quad (3.7)$$

the collision has actually occurred and is evaluated accordingly. Otherwise the collision is rejected as hypothetical (also referred to as ‘delta-collisions’) and a new distance to collision

⁴Readers interested in the derivation of the distance to collision can see ref [2], and a detailed derivation of Monte Carlo transport methods can be found in Ch. 9 of [3].

⁵Our problem assumes constant $\Sigma_{t,m}$ across material m . However, $\Sigma_{t,m}$ in reality can vary with energy, temperature, density, or changing material composition [6].

is sampled [6]. Eventually, the particle will either exit the system via the right-hand-side and be tallied for transmittance, or exit the system in some other way and not be tallied for this problem. The transmittance is averaged over all histories in the sample, and this is then repeated N_ξ times for UQ analysis.

3.3. Analytic Solution. For a problem in which $\Sigma_s(x) = 0$, i.e. attenuation-only, an analytic solution for uncollided transmittance of a normally incident beam through a slab is

$$T(\xi) = \psi(L, 1, \xi) = \exp \left[\sum_{m=1}^M \Sigma_{t,m}(\xi_m) \Delta x_m \right]. \quad (3.8)$$

The p th raw moment for the transmittance, as derived in [10], can be written as

$$\mathbb{E}[T^p] = \prod_{m=1}^d \exp[-p\bar{\Sigma}_{t,m}\Delta x_m] \frac{\sinh[p\Sigma_{t,m}\Delta x_m]}{p\Sigma_{t,m}\Delta x_m}, \quad (3.9)$$

which allows for an exact evaluations of central moments by adopting the well-known transformations from raw to central moments. For instance, for the variance, which is the second central moment, we can write

$$\text{Var}[T] = \mathbb{E}[T^2] - \mathbb{E}[T]^2. \quad (3.10)$$

Moreover, as it is also possible to compute the variance $\mathbb{E}_\xi[\sigma_{RT, N_\eta}^2]$ in closed form for this problem, this example is well suited for verification purposes.

4. Numerical Results. In this section we present the performance of the variance estimators described in the previous sections for two UQ analysis scenarios, namely attenuation-only and attenuation with scattering. We consider a 1D slab with 3 material sections⁶ and fixed boundaries between them. Each problem is solved using a fixed computational cost of $N_\xi \times N_\eta = 1500$ particle histories, however we consider different combinations of N_ξ and N_η . Moreover, we run 25 000 repetitions of the estimators, which correspond to realizations of all random variables, both ξ and η , to generate estimators' distributions and statistics.

4.1. Scenario 1: Attenuation only. In Table 4.1, we report the right boundary location, average total cross section, and deviation from the mean for the cross section for each of the material sections. In Table 4.2, we report the statistics (mean and variance) for the new estimator S^2 and previous estimator S_I^2 of $\text{Var}[T]$ where T is the calculated transmittance, obtained over 25 000 repetitions of the estimator and for different combinations of N_ξ and N_η . We also compare the calculated variance to the analytic solution outlined in Section 3.3 using the mean squared error (MSE), which measures both the bias and variance of the estimator distribution, thus providing combined metrics for both the accuracy and precision of our estimator. It should be noted again here that no matter the number of histories run for calculation of other QoI such as transmittance, the previous method [9] specifies the use of only one history (typically the first one) to calculate total polluted variance.

⁶The approach can be extended to higher number of sections without any modifications to the algorithm.

	m = 1	m = 2	m = 3
x_R	2.0	5.0	6.0
$\bar{\Sigma}_{t,m}$	0.90	0.15	0.60
$\Sigma_{t,m}^\Delta$	0.70	0.12	0.50

Table 4.1: Stochastic Attenuation Problem Parameters

(N_ξ, N_η)	(100,15)	(300,5)	(500,3)	(750,2)	Exact
$\mathbb{E}[S^2]$	5.506e-03	5.501e-03	5.519e-03	5.498e-03	5.505e-03
$\mathbb{E}[S_I^2]$	5.557e-03	5.446e-03	5.522e-03	5.508e-03	5.505e-03
$\text{Var}[S^2]$	4.328e-06	5.172e-06	7.636e-06	1.276e-05	-
$\text{Var}[S_I^2]$	4.716e-04	1.392e-04	7.270e-05	4.543e-05	-
$\text{Var}[S_I^2]/\text{Var}[S^2]$	108.96	26.91	9.52	3.56	-
$\text{MSE}[S^2]$	4.328e-06	5.172e-06	7.636e-06	1.276e-05	-
$\text{MSE}[S_I^2]$	4.716e-04	1.392e-04	7.270e-05	4.542e-05	-

Table 4.2: Parametric variance ($\text{Var}[T]$) results for the stochastic attenuation-only problem using 25000 repetitions. Note that the previous estimator [9] specifies the use of one history to calculate total polluted variance, causing the higher variance and mean squared error.

We first note that one would expect the MSE of an unbiased estimator to be equal to the variance, as it is possible to observe in Table 4.2, corroborating the unbiased nature of both estimators. We also observe from these results that for the same computational cost $N_\xi \times N_\eta = 1500$, the variance and MSE of S^2 using the novel estimator increase as the number of histories decreases. We observe the opposite using the previous estimator. Because the previous estimator's lower precision results from the use of only one history to estimate the total variance, as the number of histories gets closer to 1 this effect is minimized. Even with $\text{Var}[S^2]$ increasing as $\text{Var}[S_I^2]$ decreasing, each of the four cases shows a reduction in $\text{Var}[S^2]$ when using the new estimator over the old.

In Figure 4.1, we provide the results of the 25 000 repetitions, considering all tested combinations of N_ξ and N_η , for both estimators and we compare them with the exact solutions which is available for this problems.

The distributions from both methods centering around the analytic solution for $\text{Var}[T]$ provides additional evidence that both estimators are unbiased. However, $\text{Var}[T]$ calculated using our novel method has a tighter distribution around the analytic variance, corresponding with its higher statistical reliability. This is also evident from looking at the ratio between $\text{Var}[S_I^2]$ and $\text{Var}[S^2]$ reported in Table 4.2, which for this case varies approximately from 3 to 100. This holds even when comparing the estimators' respective most efficient cases, $\text{Var}[S_I^2](100, 15)/\text{Var}[S^2](750, 2) = 10.50$, approximately an order of magnitude of improvement. In a practical application, we would only be able to obtain a single realization for S^2 or S_I^2 ; therefore, it is preferable to use an estimator with a higher precision, *i.e.* smaller variance thus higher probability of being closer to the true statistics.

4.2. Case 2: Attenuation and scattering. For this test case, in Table 4.3 we report the right boundary location, average total cross section and deviation from its mean, and average scattering ratio $c_{s,m}$ and deviation from its mean for each of the material sections. The results of the estimators are summarized in Table 4.4. It is worth noting that though the mean variance appears to systemically change as a function of N_η , this is not the case; all of the solutions are within the statistical uncertainty, and for this series of repetitions happened to increase as N_η does. All calculated variances are higher than their attenuation-

only counterparts, caused by the inclusion of the second stochastic parameter for each of the materials, the scattering ratio. As with Case 1, $\text{Var} [S^2]$ decreases as the number of histories increases, and $\text{Var} [S_I^2]$ behaves inversely. Though $\text{Var} [S_I^2] / \text{Var} [S^2]$ is higher in Case 1 than Case 2, we still observe improvement when using the new estimator over the old, and the ratio of their respective best cases $\text{Var} [S_I^2] (100, 15) / \text{Var} [S^2] (750, 2) = 9.11$, still close to an order of magnitude of difference.

	m = 1	m = 2	m = 3
x_R	2.0	5.0	6.0
$\bar{\Sigma}_{t,m}$	0.90	0.15	0.60
$\Sigma_{t,m}^\Delta$	0.70	0.12	0.50
$\bar{c}_{s,m}$	0.50	0.50	0.50
$c_{s,m}^\Delta$	0.40	0.40	0.40

Table 4.3: Stochastic Absorption and Scattering Problem Parameters

(N_ξ, N_η)	(100,15)	(300,5)	(500,3)	(750,2)
$\mathbb{E} [S^2]$	9.689e-03	9.148e-03	8.201e-03	6.587e-03
$\mathbb{E} [S_I^2]$	9.879e-03	9.098e-03	8.345e-03	6.591e-03
$\text{Var} [S^2]$	9.143e-06	9.830e-06	1.158e-05	1.555e-05
$\text{Var} [S_I^2]$	5.481e-04	1.611e-04	8.327e-05	4.965e-05
$\text{Var} [S_I^2] / \text{Var} [S^2]$	59.95	16.39	7.19	3.19

Table 4.4: Parametric variance ($\text{Var} [T]$) results for the attenuation and scattering problem using 25000 repetitions. Note that the previous estimator [9] specifies the use of one history to calculate total polluted variance, causing the higher variance.

In Figure 4.2, we show the distributions of S^2 and \tilde{S}^2 over 25 000 repetitions for all tested combinations of (N_ξ, N_η) . The variance is about an order of magnitude larger compared to the attenuation-only case, reported in Figure 4.1. This is further evidence of the increased variability induced by the second parameter for each material section.

Although there is no analytic solution for comparison, it is evident that the variance distributions are wider when calculated using the previous method compared to those from the novel one, as expected. We also note that the advantage of the novel estimator grows as N_η increases since it can take advantage of the additional particle histories to decrease the variability of the term $\text{Var} [\tilde{S}^2]$. Moreover, the contribution of the MC RT estimator variance is better resolved and, therefore, the polluted variance and the parametric variance are closer when the number of particle histories increases.

Fig. 4.1: 1D radiation transport problem with absorption only ($d = 3$). 25 000 repetitions for the estimators: the new S^2 and the previous S^2 , [9], estimators are reported. Exact solutions are reported as vertical lines.

Fig. 4.2: 1D radiation transport problem with absorption and scattering ($d = 6$). 25 000 repetitions for the estimators: the new S^2 and the previous S^2_I , [9], estimators are reported.

5. Conclusions. In this contribution, we focused on the derivation of statistical properties for nested Monte Carlo estimators that can arise in applications involving stochasticity in the solver. In particular, we focused on radiation transport solvers that rely on a Monte Carlo method to obtain quantities of interest, *e.g.* transmittance, by tallying particle histories. We proposed a variance deconvolution approach which has the potential to improve the efficiency of parametric variance computations by taking into account the noise introduced by a limited number of particle histories. First, we demonstrated how the total variance (the variance of a quantity of interest over the space of UQ parameters and particle histories) is affected by the variance of a MC radiation transport solver. Second, we designed an unbiased estimator for the parametric variance based on the variance deconvolution. Moreover, we compared our newly derived estimator with the one previously introduced in [9] and demonstrated, through a series of numerical tests, that the new estimator has the potential to yield higher precision results. For the numerical tests, we considered the transmittance of neutral particles through a 1D slab whose material sections had uncertain properties, *i.e.* total and scattering cross sections.

Current research directions include the derivation of a closed-form solution for the estimator variance in order to study the role of the number of UQ samples and particle histories, efficient parallelization of the method for GPUs, and the integration of this strategy within larger UQ workflows such as the efficient construction of polynomial chaos expansion surrogates, following [4], and stochastic media UQ algorithms such as Conditional Point Sampling (CoPS) [13].

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